

Measuring the Magecart Attack Surface: An Empirical Analysis of Third-Party JavaScript Exposure on Sensitive Web Pages

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Abstract—The internet runs on trust: trust, between developers and the third-party services developer’s depend on, and also between users and the platform they submit their sensitive information to. And in modern web javascript is the standard client-side language, and its ability to load and execute code from remote sources under the same page namespace is both its greatest strength and also its most impactfull security weakness. A malicious or compromised third-party script provider can steal data from any page, that includes their code, accessing form fields, cookies, and DOM content without restriction.

Third-party JavaScript Inclusion is standard practice across modern web applications, but ironically the security implications on sensitive pages remain underexplored. This paper presents a measurement study of third-party JavaScript exposure across 849 sensitive web pages drawn from the Tranco top-10000 domain list. This paper finds that 52.2% of these pages include, at least one third-party script with no Subresource Integrity (SRI) protection, directly exposing users to Magecart-class credential interception. This paper further identifies the most-common and famous third-party providers, highlighting the systemic chokepoints or vulnerabilities that act as single points of failure across the corpus (dataset). The findings show that despite SRI being a very well-established defense since 2016, its adoption on the pages where it matters most, like login, and payment, and etc remains critically low, at just 4.9% of observed third-party scripts.

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern web runs on trust. When a developer includes a third-party script in their web application, they are implicitly trusting that the provider will deliver exactly the code they expect, unmodified, uncompromised, and behaving as intended. This trust model underpins the majority of the web, and it is increasingly being exploited.

Web skimming, also known as a Magecart attack, is a class of client-side attack where malicious JavaScript reads sensitive data, credentials, payment card numbers, personally identifiable information, directly from the browser’s Document Object Model (DOM) before it reaches the server. Unlike server-side breaches, these attacks are invisible to backend monitoring and leave no server logs. The only requirement for a successful attack is a malicious script running on the same page as a sensitive form.

The consequences are well documented. In 2018, attackers injected 22 lines of JavaScript into British Airways’ payment page, compromising the card data of approximately 500,000 customers over several weeks before detection [6]. The script

ran silently alongside legitimate third-party code, invisible to both users and developers.

More recently, the polyfill.io supply chain attack demonstrated this threat at a much larger scale. In February 2024, a Chinese company acquired the domain and GitHub account of the widely-used polyfill.io CDN library [4]. Following the acquisition, the domain began distributing dynamically generated malware to any site embedding `cdn.polyfill.io`, affecting over 100,000 websites simultaneously. The malware was built to evade detection: it activated only on specific mobile devices and at specific hours, stayed silent when it detected admin users or analytics tools, and used obfuscated fake Google Analytics domains to exfiltrate stolen data.

Both incidents share the same core cause: a third-party script running on sensitive pages without any integrity verification(authentication). Subresource Integrity (SRI),which was standardized by the W3C in 2016, provides exactly this verification, a cryptographic hash embedded in the script tag that the browser checks before executing any third-party script [5]. If the received content does not match the hash, the browser will no executethe script. SRI directly breaks the attack chain in both incidents above.

Despite this, SRI adoption in websites remains poorly understood, particularly on the webpages where it matters most. Earlier work has measured third-party JavaScript inclusion broadly [1] and studied the general failure of SRI and CSP adoption across the web [2], [3], [8], [9], but no study has specifically examined SRI adoption on sensitive pages: pages containing password or payment input fields, where an unprotected third-party script has direct access to user credentials.

This paper fills that gap, with the following contributions:

- 1) This paper constructs a dataset of approximately 1,000 candidate sensitive pages from the Tranco top-10000 domains, of which 849 were successfully scanned, and then conducts a systematic measurement of third-party JavaScript inclusion and SRI adoption in those sites.
- 2) This paper finds that 52.2% of sensitive pages include at least one third-party script without any SRI protection, directly exposing users to Magecart-class credential interception.
- 3) This paper identifies the top third-party providers by popularity, characterizing systemic single points of fail-

ure, and classifies sensitive pages by their level of third-party JavaScript exposure.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Third-Party JavaScript Inclusion

Third-party JavaScript inclusion is when a website loads and executes scripts hosted by a different domain, user, or organisation. Developers include these third-party scripts for analysis, advertment, payment processing, user-interface enhancement, and CDN hosted libraries.

There are two ways to include external JavaScript: downloading a local copy and serving it from the developer's own server, or instructing the browser to fetch it directly from the third-party provider at runtime.

The local copy approach gives the developer full control over what code runs in users' browsers, but it comes with maintenance overhead and cache inefficiency, which is why it is rare in practice. Remote inclusion is far more common, but it transfers control of the executed code entirely to the third-party provider. As Nikiforakis et al. established, a compromised or malicious provider can manipulate any page that includes their scripts, accessing cookies, DOM content, and form field values without restriction [1].

B. Subresource Integrity

Subresource Integrity (SRI) is a W3C security standard that lets developers specify a cryptographic hash of an expected resource directly in the HTML tag that loads it [5]. When the browser fetches the resource, it computes the hash of the received content and compares it against the value in the `integrity` attribute. If they do not match, indicating the content has been modified, the browser refuses to execute the script.

An SRI-protected script tag looks like this:

```
<script src="https://cdn.example.com/library.js"
  integrity="sha384-[hash]"
  crossorigin="anonymous"></script>
```

SRI directly addresses the trust problem in third-party inclusion. Even if a CDN is compromised, the browser rejects any modified content before it runs. The main limitation is that SRI is incompatible with dynamically generated scripts, resources whose content changes per-request cannot be pinned to a static hash, which is one of the primary structural reasons adoption remains low [8].

C. Magecart and Web Skimming

Magecart refers to both a group of threat actors and the broader class of attack techniques centred on injecting JavaScript skimmers into web pages to steal payment card data and credentials at the point of entry. The attack runs entirely in the browser: the malicious script intercepts form field values before they are submitted and exfiltrates them to an attacker-controlled server. Because it operates on the client-side, it is invisible to server-side monitoring and intrusion detection systems.

The primary delivery mechanism for Magecart attacks is compromised or malicious third-party scripts. By targeting a single widely-used CDN or analytics provider, attackers can achieve simultaneous exposure across thousands of sites, as demonstrated by both the British Airways breach [6] and the polyfill.io incident [4].

III. RELATED WORK

Nikiforakis et al. conducted the first large-scale study of third-party JavaScript inclusion, crawling the top 10,000 Alexa domains and characterizing the extent of remote script dependencies [1]. Their work established the systemic risk model this paper adopts, proving that third-party script concentration creates a massive, simultaneous attack surface across thousands of popular sites. Their study predates the 2016 standardization of SRI, so they did not account for SRI and sensitive page contexts.

Lauinger et al. measured the use of outdated JavaScript libraries across the web, finding a very high dependency on libraries with known vulnerabilities [2]. And so due to there research being conducted before SRI became standard in 2016, due to which their focus is on library staleness as a risk factor rather than real-time supply chain interception, leaving a gap in understanding how SRI protects high-risk user data.

Weissbacher et al. examined the adoption of Content Security Policy (CSP) across the web, finding that deployment was severely limited by developer friction and compatibility issues with existing third-party dependencies [3]. Their analysis extends to SRI as a related mechanism and similarly finds low adoption, though not specifically on sensitive pages.

More directly relevant, Chapuis et al. conducted the first large-scale longitudinal study of SRI adoption, analyzing approximately 3 billion URLs over 3.5 years [8]. They found SRI adoption grew from less than 1% in 2017 to just 3.4% by 2019. A related measurement study for the same by Khodayari et al. also found similarly low adoption and proposed a browser extension to enforce client-side SRI policies to mitigate this low adoption [9]. Both studies are focused on large and broad web-matrix and not on specialized sensitive pages.

No prior work has actually measured all these points together: sensitive page context, third-party script inclusion, and SRI adoption. Despite them being the most sensitive and important, pages where credential interception actually matters, the pages with password and payment fields, these pages have not been studied or researched as a distinct topic. And this paper addresses that directly.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Corpus Construction

This paper constructed its corpus(dataset) by fetching the Tranco top-10000 domain list, a research-grade aggregate ranking drawn from multiple traffic and DNS sources [7]. For each domain, five common login paths were probed: `/login`, `/signin`, `/account`, `/user/login`, and `/auth`. A page was retained if it returned an HTTP 200 response and contained at least one `<input type="password">` element

in the response body, indicating a credential input form. This process identified approximately 1,000 candidate sensitive pages. Of these, 849 were successfully scanned; the remaining 151 timed out or returned errors during the Playwright scan phase, consistent with sites that block headless browsers or impose rate limits.

B. Sensitive Page Classification

This paper defines a sensitive page as any publicly accessible web page containing at least one password input field. This definition is intentionally conservative: it captures login pages directly and excludes pages where sensitive input may be injected dynamically after the initial page load. Classification is DOM-based, derived from static HTML analysis of the HTTP response, not from JavaScript execution.

C. Data Collection Pipeline

Data collection was performed using Playwright v1.44.0 running headless Chromium, containerized in Docker for reproducibility. For each URL in the corpus, the page was loaded and all `<script src="...">` elements were extracted from the rendered DOM, recording the script URL and the value of the `integrity` attribute where present. A script was classified as third-party if its origin differed from the page origin. A script was classified as SRI-protected if its `integrity` attribute was non-empty. Pages were scanned with a concurrency of eight simultaneous browser contexts and a timeout of 25 seconds per page.

D. Metrics

This paper defines three research questions:

RQ1: What percentage of sensitive pages include at least one unprotected third-party script?

RQ2: Which third-party origins appear most frequently across sensitive pages, and what is their aggregate site reach?

RQ3: How do sensitive pages distribute across exposure categories: fully exposed, partially protected, and fully protected?

A page is considered exposed if it contains a password field and at least one third-party script with no SRI protection. This represents the minimum condition for a Magecart-class attack to succeed via third-party script compromise.

Ethics note: All data collection was passive and observational. No scripts were executed beyond normal browser page loading. No vulnerabilities were exploited. All pages in the corpus are publicly accessible without authentication.

V. RESULTS

A. RQ1: SRI Adoption on Sensitive Pages

Of the 849 sensitive pages in this paper’s corpus, 443 (52.2%) include at least one third-party script with no SRI protection. Across all third-party scripts observed, 244 carried a valid `integrity` attribute while 4,777 did not, yielding an overall SRI adoption rate of 4.9% among third-party scripts on sensitive pages.

Fig. 1: SRI adoption among third-party scripts on sensitive pages.

As shown in Fig. 1, the overwhelming majority of third-party scripts on sensitive pages carry no integrity protection. A compromise of any of these providers gives an attacker the ability to execute arbitrary JavaScript on a page with direct DOM access to password fields, with no browser-level mechanism to detect or block it.

Notably, this paper’s 4.9% adoption rate on sensitive pages is consistent with Chapuis et al.’s finding of 3.4% adoption across all pages in 2019 [8]. Five years later, on the pages where the stakes are highest, adoption has not meaningfully improved.

B. RQ2: Third-Party Origin Analysis

Fig. 2 shows the top 15 third-party origins by number of sensitive pages that include them. The most prevalent origin, `www.googletagmanager.com`, appears across 282 pages in this paper’s corpus, more than a third of all successfully scanned pages.

The top 15 origins fall into four categories: analytics and tracking, advertising networks, CDN and infrastructure services, and authentication providers.

The most common origin is `www.googletagmanager.com`, appearing on 282 out of 849 pages. What makes this particularly significant is that GTM does not just run a single script, it dynamically loads additional third-party scripts at runtime based on tag configurations. This means even if a developer attempted to use SRI on the GTM tag itself, all subsequently injected scripts would bypass integrity verification entirely. GTM’s presence on a page effectively creates an un-auditable script execution surface that SRI cannot protect against.

Analytics and tracking providers dominate the top origins overall: Google Tag Manager, Google Analytics, Microsoft Clarity, and Bing Ads account for a substantial share of appearances. Advertising networks follow:

Fig. 2: Top 15 third-party origins by sensitive page count.

Facebook, Reddit, LinkedIn, and Google Ads. Cloudflare appears twice as distinct services, but protection (`challenges.cloudflare.com`) and web analytics (`static.cloudflareinsights.com`), together covering 222 pages. Google authentication infrastructure (`accounts.google.com`, `www.gstatic.com`, `www.google.com`) appears on 192 pages combined, meaning these scripts load directly alongside password input fields. Two additional origins of note are `cdn.cookiecave.com`, a cookie consent management platform appearing on 36 pages, and `cdn.jsdelivr.net`, an open-source CDN appearing on 33 pages, neither of which carry SRI protection.

Critically, none of the top 15 origins carry SRI protection. Every high-reach origin in these results has `has_sri = 0`. The most widely included third-party scripts on sensitive pages are simultaneously the least protected: a compromise of any single top-five origin would affect a large portion of this paper’s corpus with no browser-level integrity check in place.

C. RQ3: Page Exposure Classification

Fig. 3 classifies the 703 password pages in this paper’s corpus by their exposure profile. 302 pages (43.0%) are fully exposed, they include third-party scripts with no SRI protection on any of them. 141 pages (20.1%) are partially protected, at least one third-party script carries SRI but at least one does not. 44 pages (6.3%) are fully protected, all third-party scripts carry valid SRI attributes. 216 pages include no third-party scripts at all.

The proportion of fully exposed pages, 43.0%, represents the direct Magecart attack surface in this paper’s corpus. More than four in ten sensitive pages scanned could be compromised via a single third-party script provider with no browser-level defence available to the user.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Why SRI Adoption Is Low

The results show that SRI adoption on sensitive pages is critically low despite the mechanism being standardised since

Fig. 3: Classification of pages by SRI exposure profile.

2016. Several structural factors explain this. First, SRI is incompatible with dynamically generated scripts, resources whose content is generated per-request, such as personalised analytics snippets or A/B testing scripts, cannot be pinned to a static hash. Many of the high-reach origins in this paper’s corpus fall into this category, most notably Google Tag Manager. Second, implementing SRI requires a deliberate build step to generate and embed hashes, adding friction to development workflows. Third, CDN providers do not consistently surface SRI hashes alongside their embed codes, placing the burden entirely on the developer [9].

B. High-Reach Origins as Systemic Chokepoints

The concentration of third-party dependencies on a small number of origins represents a systemic risk that individual sites cannot mitigate on their own. The polyfill.io incident demonstrated this directly: a single domain acquisition exposed over 100,000 sites simultaneously [4]. This paper’s corpus shows a similar concentration pattern: the top five origins account for 667 combined script-page appearances across the corpus, and every one of them lacks SRI protection. A targeted attack on any single top-five origin would have broad, immediate consequences for user credentials with no existing browser-level defence to stop it.

C. Limitations

This paper has several limitations that scope its findings. The corpus is drawn from the Tranco top-10000 domains, biasing it toward large, well-known sites; smaller sites and regional domains are underrepresented. The sensitive page classification is static and DOM-based, meaning pages that inject password fields dynamically via JavaScript after load are not captured. Script inclusion is measured at a single point in time; third-party dependencies change over time and this snapshot may not reflect current or historical exposure. Finally, this paper measures inclusion and SRI presence, not actual script behaviour, and cannot confirm whether any observed third-party script would in practice access form field data.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper measured third-party JavaScript inclusion and SRI adoption across 849 sensitive web pages drawn from the Tranco top-10000 domains. The findings show that 52.2% of these pages are directly exposed to Magecart-class attacks through unprotected third-party scripts, and that a small number of high-reach origins, none carrying SRI protection, represent systemic single points of failure across the corpus. At 4.9%, SRI adoption on sensitive pages has not improved meaningfully since 2019 [8], despite the mechanism being available for nearly a decade. At minimum, any page handling password or payment input should enforce SRI on all third-party script inclusions. Future work should expand this measurement to a larger corpus across multiple time snapshots, and explore whether a community-maintained integrity registry for third-party CDN scripts could lower the barrier to runtime verification at scale.

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